

Complexation of Sodium and Potassium with 1,10-Phenanthroline in Solution

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Employing organic salts, ML (where M=Na and K; and L=2-aminobenzoate (Anth), 2-hydroxybenzoate (Sal), 2,6-dihydroxybenzoate (HO-Sal), interaction of M with 1, 10-phenanthroline (PHEN) has been followed employing U. V. spectroscopy in ethanol and 100 MHz H nmr spectroscopy in DMSO-d₆. Employing conductivity measurements, the interacting ability of PHEN with M in acetone has been compared with ligands such as 4, 7-diphenyl-PHEN, 2, 2'-bipyridyl, 2, 2'-biquinoline, and benzo-15-crown-5 (CROWN). The results of all the three techniques indicate that M-PHEN interaction is favoured as ion-association of the M⁺L⁻ salt decreases, i.e., as the nucleophilicity of L decreases; conversely, M-PHEN interaction is followed by loosening of the M⁺L⁻ ion pair. The results also indicate that in acetone, Na interacts more strongly with the 'anionic' N-donor PHEN whereas K with the electrically neutral O-donor CROWN.

COORDINATION chemistry of alkali (M⁺) and alkaline earth (M²⁺) cations (M) is being extensively investigated¹ with the purpose to understand the mysterious role of Na, K, Ca and Mg in biological systems.^{2,3} In the solid phase, the ligation of M with minimolecular (MIM) and macromolecular (MCM) ligands can be detected with rather a degree of confidence employing diffraction techniques.¹ However, chemical information about M obtained from the model experiments can be used with confidence to the understanding of their role in natural systems only if the former is collected from the solution state. Unfortunately, however, it is difficult to follow complexation of M in solution, for M-ligand bonds are usually weak and M are devoid of magnetic and convenient spectroscopic properties. In solution, some information can be collected for the M-MCM systems using diverse type of electrometric techniques,¹ for MCM are exceptionally strong multidentates. With the conventional MIM, only the special techniques such as ⁷Li and ²³Na nmr spectroscopy can provide some information^{4,5} but practicability of such techniques is highly limited.

The present author attempted to follow M⁺-PHEN (M⁺=Na and K) interaction in different polar organic media as follows :

(i) Authentic ML(PHEN)_n complexes were synthesised⁶⁻⁸ where the M-PHEN interaction was regulated by using L of varying nucleophilicity, viz., 2-hydroxy-benzoate (Sal) and 2,6-dihydroxybenzoate (HO-Sal). The complexes were dissolved in DMSO-d₆ and 100 MHz H nmr spectra of the PHEN protons were recorded.

(ii) The authentic ML(PHEN)_n.xH₂O (L=2-aminobenzoate (Anth) and Sal; x=0 for Na(Sal) and 2 for rest) complexes were isolated. They were dissolved in ethanol and u.v. spectra were recorded.

(iii) Conductivity (Ohm⁻¹ cm²) measurements of ML and the ML-G (G=benzo-15-crown-5 (CROWN), PHEN, and the related ligands; and L=2-nitrophenolate (Onp), Sal, HO-Sal, and Anth) systems were carried out in acetone where M-G interaction was favoured by using excess G and the poorly solvating medium for the investigations.

Experimental

H nmr Spectroscopy. The complexes Na (ClO₄) (PHEN)₂, M(HO-Sal)(PHEN)₂, Na(Sal)(PHEN)₂ and K(Sal)(PHEN)₂.2aq were synthesised as described^{6,9} and dissolved in DMSO-d₆ (about 50 mg per ml). Spectra were recorded at 20° using TMS as internal standard employing a Varian 100 MHz Spectrometer.

U.V. Spectroscopy: The complexes Na(Sal)(PHEN)₂, K(Sal)(PHEN)₂.2aq and M(AntH)(PHEN)₂.2aq were synthesised as described⁸ and dissolved in ethanol. The spectra were recorded in the range 400 to 210 nm employing UNICAM SP 600 spectrophotometer. Using ethanol as medium, the spectra of the parent ML salts and the acids (HL) were also recorded.

Conductivity Measurements: Conductivities (Ohm⁻¹cm²) of some ML salts were measured employing 10⁻³ M solutions in acetone at 22±1°. The measurements were repeated after the addition of 20 moles of G for each mole of the ML. The

(PHEN,HL) species were synthesised by a 1:1 reaction of the concerned HL with PHEN in ethanol or 90% aqueous-ethanol⁸ and conductivities of the $10^{-3}M$ acetic solutions of these species were also measured at $22 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

H nmr Results : The $H_{2,9}$, $H_{4,7}$ and $H_{8,8}$ protons of PHEN showed up respective quartets around 9.14, 8.51 and 7.78 ppm whereas the magnetically equivalent protons, $H_{6,6}$, which do not undergo spin coupling with the protons in the adjacent rings,^{10,11} show a strong singlet at 8.00 ppm. Corresponding signals for the compounds $M(\text{Sal})(\text{PHEN})_n \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ appeared around 8.1, 8.5, 7.8 and 8.0 ppm, respectively, i.e., not significantly away from those due to the free ligand. The signals for the complexes $M(\text{HO-Sal})(\text{PHEN})_2$, no doubt, also appeared around the same position but all the three quartets showed comparatively more complicated splittings. This effect was even more pronounced for the complex $\text{Na}(\text{ClO}_4)(\text{PHEN})_2$.

The similarity of the spectra of PHEN and the $M(\text{Sal})$ complexes can be attributed to three reasons, viz., (i) Sal is a bidentate anionic charge neutraliser and competes strongly with PHEN, (ii) DMSO-d_6 is strongly hydrolytic towards the M^+ -PHEN bond, and (iii) the inductive effect of the M^+ -PHEN interaction is transmitted from the nitrogen atoms to the resonating protons through two sigma bonds. In the case of $M(\text{HO-Sal})$ complexes, HO-Sal behaves comparatively self-stabilised due to two intramolecular hydrogen bonds¹² and offers a weaker competition to PHEN so that a stronger effect of the M^+ -PHEN interaction is recorded. For the $\text{Na}(\text{ClO}_4)$ complex—where ClO_4^- is completely spherical—the effect of the M^+ -PHEN interaction is recorded still more clearly. This indicates that M^+ -PHEN interaction in solution can be favoured as the charge neutralising anion behaves self-stabilised.

The foregoing point is confirmed by the conductivity results of the (PHEN,HL) species. The (PHEN,HL) species are complexes of PHEN where

H^+ works for M^+ . Out of the species derived for HO-SalH (51.3), SalH (1.9), BenzH (0.50) (BenzH = benzoic acid), AnthH (0.67), OnpH (0.3), 2,4-dinitrophenol (4.47), and 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (65.5), only the first and the last have been found to be most highly conducting as evident from the values in parentheses. This indicates that in these two cases the proton has been completely transferred (complexed) to PHEN. Unlike the other species, which exist as $(\text{PHEN},\text{H}^+\text{L}^-)$ these two species appear to exist as $(\text{PHEN},\text{H}^+)\text{L}^-$ and it is due to the most highly self-stabilised state of HO-Sal and 2,4,6-trinitrophenolate.

The effect of change of the solvent on M^+ -PHEN interaction cannot be studied with the help of the H nmr technique, for the very spectrum of PHEN is found to be sensitive to the nature of the solvent; in DMSO-d_6 - D_2O (7:3), for example, the quartets due to $H_{2,9}$ and $H_{8,8}$ become broad bands and the one due to $H_{4,7}$ is reduced to a doublet.

Ultra-Violet Spectroscopic Results : In addition to the strong absorptions at about 325, 265 and 228 nm, which can be attributed to PHEN liberated from the decomposition of the complexes in ethanol, an additional peak for $\text{K}(\text{Sal})(\text{PHEN})_2, 2\text{aq}$ (290), $\text{Na}(\text{Sal})(\text{PHEN})_2$ (287), $\text{K}(\text{Anth})(\text{PHEN})_2, 2\text{aq}$ (311), and $\text{Na}(\text{Anth})(\text{PHEN})_2, 2\text{aq}$ (308) was noted as shown in parentheses. Each such peak is 7 to 10 nm towards the high energy side of the peak due to the respective parent salt (Table 1). These results are the same as obtained from the spectral study of the $\text{ML}+\text{PHEN}$ synthetic mixtures⁶ in the same medium but then the blue shifts were attributed to an enhanced ion-pairing of $M^+\text{L}^-$ in the presence of PHEN, for it was known¹³ that a more highly ion-paired nitrophenol (H^+L^-) absorbs on the blue side compared to its comparatively weakly ion-paired metal-nitrophenolates ($M^+\text{L}^-$). However, conductivity studies (below) show that M^+ -PHEN interaction leads to the loosening of the $M^+\text{L}^-$ ion pair and H nmr studies (above) show that loosening of the $M^+\text{L}^-$ ion-pair facilitates M^+ -PHEN interaction. This necessitated a new interpretation for U. V. results of the $\text{ML}(\text{PHEN})_n$

TABLE 1—SHOWING ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTIONS (IN ETHANOL) FOR L IN THE PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT COUNTER CATIONS

	Counter cation				
	H^+	Na^+	$\text{Na}(\text{PHEN})_2^+$	K^+	$\text{K}(\text{PHEN})_2^+$
Benz	273 nm	269 nm		270 nm	
Sal	304	296	287	297	290
Sal-OH	315	307		308	
Anth	337	317	308	318	311
2-nitrophenolate	347	417		415	
2-cyanophenolate	297	308		308	

and ML+PHEN systems and hence a detailed spectral study of a series of HL and their salts.

Ultra-violet spectra of some HL and the analogous ML salts (Table 1) show that λ_{\max} of L in ML can appear on the red or the blue side of the λ_{\max} due to L in HL depending upon the nature of the anionic site and the nature of the additional substituents on the nucleus of L. The λ_{\max} for metal 2-nitrophenolates and 2-cyanophenolates, for example, appears on the red side of the one due to their parent acids whereas that of the metal benzoates appears on the blue side of the latter; the blue shift in the latter case is increasingly high in the order BenzH, SalH and HO-SalH.

From the foregoing results it is evident that for the NO_2 and CN substituted phenols a red shift noted after the salification is because $-\text{O}^-$ site is more electron supplying than $-\text{OH}$ group wherein the effect overcompensates even the effect due to the presence of the electron withdrawing $-\text{CN}$ and NO_2 groups. In the case of the benzoic acids, a blue shift noted after salification is because $-\text{COO}^-$ is less electron withdrawing than $-\text{COOH}$ group¹⁴; the effect is enhanced in the order BenzH, SalH and HO-SalH, for an electron supply $-\text{OH}$ group is being successively added in the molecule. If PHEN is also present in a solution of M^+L^- then due to stabilisation (complexation) of M^+ , the anionic site of an L can behave more independently. Consequently, a further red shift for a phenolate and a blue shift for a benzoate is expected to take place. The blue shift for the complexes of the metal benzoates in the present and in the earlier⁶ work, therefore, indicates the formation of loose $\text{M}(\text{PHEN})_n^+\text{L}^-$ ion pair and a detectable complexation of M^+ with PHEN in ethanol. The rather small shift (7–10 nm) has been considered significant because difference in λ_{\max} of HL and M^+L^- is even less in most cases (Table 1) although difference in dissociation of the two species should be significant.

Conductivity Results : Table 2 shows the results. The ionic mobilities of the ML salts were significantly enhanced in the presence of PHEN and CROWN, of the NaL salts in the presence of PHEN and of the KL salts in the presence of CROWN. 4,7-diphenyl-PHEN produced detectable effects whereas 2, 2'-bipyridyl and 2,2'-biquinoline were practically ineffective.

Increments in the conductivity of the MX_n salts on the addition of OMPA^{15} have been attributed to M-OMPA interaction in solution. In the present case also increments due to the addition of G may be attributed to $\text{M}^+\text{-G}$ interaction and to the consequent loose pair, $\text{M}(\text{G})_n^+\text{L}^-$, formation. Conductivity enhancement due to the addition of excess G cannot be mainly due to changes in the dielectric constant of the medium because (i) for a given ligand (PHEN or CROWN) conductivity of M^+L^- changes as predicted in view of the nature of M^+ and L^- , and (ii) for the same molar concentration of the rather poor ligands related to PHEN there is absolutely no change in the conductivity of M^+L^- . In the case of the MX_n -OMPA systems the conductivity increments were found to be influenced by the nature of X; they were enhanced in the order Cl^- , NO_3^- , ClO_4^- which is also the order of decreasing basicity (nucleophilicity) of these anions. The present studies indicate that the increments produced on the addition of PHEN are distinctly high for the $\text{M}(\text{HO-Sal})$ salts than for $\text{M}(\text{Sal})$ as if the more self-stabilised HO-Sal allows a more effective stabilisation of M^+ with PHEN—a conclusion also drawn from the H nmr results.

Sodium is a hard acid in contrast to potassium and in consistence with the HSAB concept¹⁶ is likely to interact strongly with the hard (anionic)¹⁷ bases. In view of a high (.377 unit) negative charge carried by the nitrogen atoms¹⁸ PHEN can be considered as an anionic bidentate. The so-called 'anion-philic' property of Na^+ can be satisfied by

TABLE 2—SHOWING IONIC MOBILITY ($\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) OF SOME ML SALTS IN ACETONE AND OF THE SAME IN THE PRESENCE OF SOME ELECTRICALLY NEUTRAL LIGANDS AT $22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

ML	Cation	Ionic Mobility (control)	Ionic mobility in the presence of :		
			PHEN	4,7-diphenyl-PHEN	CROWN
M(Sal)	Sodium	25.0	54.5	34.0	36.0
	Potassium	60.0	67.3	62.5	121.5
M(HO-Sal)	Sodium	60.0	89.5	73.5	80.0
	Potassium	83.3	88.0	84.7	100.5
M(Anth)	Sodium	7.5 ^a	19.0	...	18.0
	Potassium	21.5	26.5	...	69.5
M(2-NP)	Sodium	10.0 ^a	23.0	...	19.0
	Potassium	29.5	38.5	...	81.0

^a ... , not studied. 2, 2'-bipyridyl and 2, 2'-biquinoline exercised no effect on the ionic mobility of ML. This low conducting salt was also difficultly soluble in acetone.

interaction with PHEN. This explains why in spite of strong ion-association (initial low conductivities), the Na^+L^- salts, as against K^+L^- salts, exhibit high conductivity increments on the addition of PHEN*.

Potassium is a cation of low charge density and interacts weakly with the anionic species, i.e., charge neutralising anion and the solvating liquid. Instead of PHEN, therefore, it is expected to interact preferably with CROWN during the interaction of which a powerful macrocyclic effect^{19,20} is also incorporated. The K^+ -CROWN interaction is so favourable that in the presence of CROWN the KX and KL salts invariably undergo complete charge separation through the formation of the $\text{K}(\text{CROWN})_2$ sandwich.^{1,21,22} It is this difference of potassium from sodium due to which the K^+L^- salts, unlike the Na^+L^- salts, exhibit high conductivity increments in the presence of the electrically neutral CROWN.

Because of their own structural reasons, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 2,2'-biquinoline prefer to exist in trans-form.^{23,24} The transition cations^{25,26} and even thallos⁸, which shows a potential for a covalency in the Tl-N bond,^{27,28} form stable complexes with these ligands while stabilising successfully their cis-form. Since these ligands do not make any effect on the conductivity of the ML salts, they do not create stable contacts with M^+ inspite of their higher anionic nature than PHEN¹⁸. Obviously, the degree of covalency in the M-N bond is low as a consequence of which the cis-form of the ligands is not stabilised against the destabilisation caused by the steric hindrance due to 3,3'-hydrogens. 4,7-diphenyl-PHEN works as a depolarised PHEN due to the phenyl substituents and hence a weak ligand.

All the three techniques show that during complexation of M^+ the role of the counter anion is dominant as concluded earlier^{8,21,22,29} from synthetic work with s-block cations in general. It is unlike noted during complexation of the transition cations and, understandably, owes its origin to HSAB relationship¹⁸, viz., soft ligands displace hard (anionic) ligands from the coordination sphere of the soft transition cations whereas hard ligands displace soft ligands from the coordination sphere of the hard s-block cations.

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* Recent conductometric solution stability studies (N. S. Poonia and A. Jayakumar, to be published) in dry acetone indicate that log K values for 1:1 ML-PHEN complexes are higher for Na (2.69 and 2.59) for 2,4-dinitrophenolato and Sal, respectively than for K (1.34 and 0.27, respectively).